

Designing an innovative toolkit for assessing user acceptance of border control technologies

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Abstract

Border authorities are constantly looking for more efficient and effective uses of technology in order to increase travelers' satisfaction and enhance security of the borders. In the EU, a great deal of effort has been put into the development of Smart Border control technologies (SBCTs) to make border checks quicker and more efficient as well as reducing the cost. However, the effects of SBCTs may remain poorer than expected due to many challenges including (not limited to) the low usage rates and the user acceptance. In this paper, we will provide a state-of-the-art approach, as dealing with missing or incomplete data enabled us to come forward with an innovative idea – a social sensing toolkit. Its main purpose is related to accessing and assessing travelers' and border control staff's perceptions, emotional states, and social interactions in order to determine whether or not the border technology will be adopted and accepted, and if so, how effectively. Border authorities will use the knowledge provided from the toolkit while monitoring and predicting acceptance on the new technologies, securing positive societal impact with the final goal of maximizing border control process efficiency and improving their decision making.

Keywords: smart border control, social sensing, technology acceptance, synthetic data, decision making

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1. Introduction

Smart Border control technologies (SBCTs) are defined as technologies that allow travelers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks and are based on automated risk assessment and/or verification processes [1]. An example of such technologies is the e-passport gates [2], which are border-controlled automated self-service barriers located at checkpoints in several European airports.

System acceptance and usage is increasingly viewed as an important element for the measurement of information systems success. In the past, many different theoretical approaches have been applied and designed to explain, predict and increase user acceptance of information systems, considered critical as previous research on technology acceptance highlights that the lack of user acceptance of technology can lead to loss of money and resources.

On the other hand, the increasing popularity of online social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc. have provided people with the platforms for collecting and analyzing large volumes of user-generated information [3]. The information extracted from these platforms can thus provide a considerable support when dealing with missing or incomplete real-time data.

This paper will try to shed light into the different aspects connecting human behavior and technology, focusing on the border control environment, between travelers and border control staff facing the existing or future technologies in use. The next section will provide more details around the main aspects of this research work, focusing on SBCTs, technology acceptance, agent-based modeling and simulation, and the social sensing part. Section 3 will discuss the Methodology followed on the current work, while section 4 will provide some of the preliminary results achieved so far. The final section will conclude the paper and provide some suggestions for the future work ahead.

2. Related works

In this section, we will discuss about the research done so far in the distinct disciplines surrounding the research problem in question.

Smart Border Control Technologies

The world is facing an unprecedented global health, social and economic emergency because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic had a negative impact on world scheduled passenger traffic for the year 2020, compared to 2019 levels [4]. As in 2021, worldwide traffic has an upward trend due to the COVID-19 vaccine; border control will have to be maintained, with a similar workforce having a substantially higher workload. Increasing passenger numbers also imply increased security and safety risks. With a higher passenger throughput, it will be more challenging to satisfy customers' (travelers) high service standards. The adoption of innovative technologies is one approach to accommodate future increases in passenger traffic while maintaining high standards of security, safety, and service.

There are multiple examples of SBCTs, with E-gates briefly mentioned in the previous section. While border agents and land/airport management regard e-passport gates as a safe and convenient alternative to traditional border checking and crossing, not all travelers choose to use these new self-service technologies. Passengers are unable or unwilling to use self-service systems for a variety of reasons such as: 1) lack of awareness, 2) difficulty in use, 3) privacy and data protection concerns, 4) lack of technological background, 5) low educational background, 5) different cultures, 6) gate design, 7) passenger's age, 8) gender, 9) nationality and such [5].

Another example is the BorderXpress Technology, which allows travelers to complete the administrative requirements of border control by using biometric-enabled kiosks as part of an efficient two-step process. This technology is designed to enhance the security and safety of the border by complementing the expertise of the border guards [6].

EasyPass is an automated border control system designed firstly for third-country nationals when entering Germany [7], while it became available to U.S citizens just recently. Travelers can quickly accomplish border control on their own. The automated border control system has several advantages, including the fact that it is extremely secure, simple to use and speeds up border crossings [7]. Also, this procedure may be very useful for frequent travelers as a simple, quick, and easy alternative as the border checks are largely automated.

The BKC-KORDON system is intended to control the flow of passengers and vehicles crossing the state border and can be applied to automobile, air, sea and pedestrian crossing points [8]. On the other side, the Smart Tunnel Technology, using facial recognition, allows travelers to complete the passport control procedure within 15 seconds and without the need for human intervention [9]. Passengers must show their passports and IDs at check-in; however, they can complete their passport control without the need of them until they reach the gates. So, smart tunnel technology can improve the conditions of the entire journey in terms of speed as it will be like a walk-through [9].

Finally, Aruba Happy Flow, which has been implemented in Aruba Airport, is a new experience for travelers that allows for a touchless, streamlined airport journey [10]. Travel documents are only required at check-in while the passenger's identity is checked, and a virtual identity is created. Following check-in, the passenger goes through baggage drop-off, pass security access, border control, and facial recognition to board the plane without having to show any travel document [11].

User technology acceptance

Users' attitudes influence the adoption and the acceptance of emerging technologies, which is referred to as Technology Acceptance. The technology acceptance model (TAM) is an information theory that models the adoption and usage of technology by individual persons, designed to test technology acceptance in a proper way [12]. According to this model, the success of the new technology adoption is based on positive attitudes towards two measures: 1) perceived utility and 2) perceived ease of use. The model has been expanded and updated several times, but the original version is still used and widely accepted as a leading model in understanding users' actions towards technology.

Furthermore, because of the development of various competing acceptance models, in 2003, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was developed [13]. Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence and Facilitating Conditions are the four components identified as determining factors for behavioral intention. The influence of the four aforementioned factors is moderated by gender, age, experience and voluntariness of use.

As for border control technologies, there is no standardization of the main components, with user interfaces still being under development. These technologies are not user-friendly because instructions aren't understood by first-time users [14]. In addition, information and clear signs about how the border control technologies are used by passengers play an important role in increasing general awareness on the former, encouraging passengers to use the system and guide them successfully through the process.

User acceptance demands that the users perceive a real need for the e-gates (e.g., convenience) and that the system is easy to use. This is particularly true when the users need to interact with new technologies infrequently or in unusual complex situations, such as travelling in an unknown context, under stress and fatigue [15]. Users are currently confused about how to interact with unfamiliar and various e-gates due to significant component differences.

Acceptance modelling based on TAM or UTAUT in the context of border control technologies focuses on specific aspects of border control systems, such as biometrics. The authors in [16] explore the factors that influence the behavioral intention to accept biometrics. The proposed model identifies the links between factors such as innovativeness, trust, and privacy concerns), antecedent factors (such as beliefs about the technology and other variables such as social influence and facilitating conditions, as well as the two subsequent factors of intentions to accept and to recommend using the biometric system.

Agent-based modeling & simulation

Simulation tools are increasingly being used in various research topics in the social and behavioral sciences to map and predict outcomes that would otherwise be difficult to achieve across a wide range of situations. In this context, simulation is primarily seen as a feasible method for visualizing or validating specific theories after performing many runs with sets of predefined values matching possible real-world cases.

An agent-based model, at its simplest level, consists of a set of agents and the interactions between them. Even a simple agent-based model can display complex behavior patterns [17] and provide helpful information about the dynamics of the real-world system it mimics.

A typical agent-based model contains three main elements:

- Agents, encompassing a possibly heterogeneous behavioral specification.
- An environment, supplying agents with their perceptions and enabling their actions.
- Rules governing each agent's behavior and its local interactions with other agents and with the environment.

ABMS is being applied to many areas, spanning human social, physical and biological systems, while some examples are analyzed further below.

One of the domains affected is education. Caillou and Sebag [18] implemented an ABMS application to investigate how universities recruit the best employee candidates with high confidence, while Zheng and Lei [19] used ABMS to study talent management to resolve issues relating to knowledge innovation and academic impact in universities.

The authors in [20] proposed a microscopic modelling approach for air transport technology, with the results showing that the proposed approach could be used to model some important characteristics of air traffic technology, such as runway capacity restrictions.

In healthcare, ABMS was used to predict the effects of patients' derivation policies in emergency departments, as in [21]. The experiment is a clear example of the benefits of using simulation as the core component of a decision support system that aids healthcare managers to make the best-informed decisions possible and making better use of resources.

In tourism, an ABMS was used to model possible futures for a market in sub-orbital space tourism, as in [22]. Each agent represents an entity within the space industry, such as consumers, producers, the government, etc., that provides or demands different products and services.

There are many more domains and publications where ABMS is being used, but, based on our research so far, none of them include border control technologies or studying the level of user technology acceptance in this domain.

Agent-based modeling and simulation (ABMS) provides several advantages compared to other modelling techniques. To begin with, it can capture emergent phenomena. Then, it provides an environment in which naturally occurring systems can be studied [23]. For example, modelling how people move around a city is a more natural approach to modelling crowd behavior than using simultaneous equations to represent the former. Finally, ABMS is flexible [23], as the number of agents and their behaviors can be easily changed, which is important for conducting simulation experiments. For all the reasons mentioned above, ABMS was chosen as relevant for our research problem.

Furthermore, an advantage of using ABMS is that with simulation, travelers' behavior can be predicted, while due to some ethical challenges, there is not the possibility to try everything on real time. There are several tools that can be used for supporting the ABMS activities, while more details will be provided in the next section, Methodology.

Social sensing

In general, social sensing refers to a set of sensing and data collection examples in which data are collected from humans or devices. To provide situation-awareness to applications, social sensing services use humans as sensor carriers, sensor operators, and sensors themselves.

As for application domains, social sensing is being applied to many areas, such as healthcare, smart buildings, mobile sensing, behavior analysis etc., with a selection of the studies analyzed further below. Social sensing has been widely used in the domain of healthcare, as in [24], where authors implemented social sensing to investigate the impact of social interactions within real-world face-to-face networks on BMI and weight changes in a co-located student community.

In [25], the authors proposed a framework for highly distributed and user-centric air quality monitoring, designed to involve the citizen in multiple stages of the monitoring process. The goal of the study was to enable individuals to monitor their exposure to air pollution, at the same time contributing to the construction of a map of the state of urban air quality through the sharing of data.

In another study, Kibanov et al. [26] investigate the opportunities that social media sensing offers for improved management of fire and haze disasters. Specifically, Twitter was analyzed as the primary data source for haze disaster management by extracting complementary and supplementary information and hotspot and air quality data were used to interpret further and verify the results of the study.

Avvenuti et al. [27] mentioned the possibility of predicting natural disasters using social media data. This study showed a strong correlation between earthquake intensity and tweet-derived predictors that means Twitter as social sensing sources play a significant role in predicting natural disasters.

In another study, Madan et al. [28], use mobile phone-based co-location and communication sensing to measure characteristic behavior changes in symptomatic individuals. This study showed that mobile sensing could play an important role in modelling epidemiological contagion without medical health reports.

D'Andrea et al. [29] present a real-time monitoring system for traffic event detection from Twitter stream analysis. This study showed that in the domain of traffic monitoring, social media sources such as Twitter could be used for traffic event detection in real-time before online traffic news websites.

Although there is not such research work available in the domain of border control technologies, previous applications and methodologies of social sensing at different domains, will help support their usage further in the former domain, as technology acceptance will be monitored considering the different behavioral patterns of the travelers and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems.

3. Methodology

The main methodology in this paper consists of the process around the design of the social sensing toolkit, with the main purpose related to assessing travelers' and border control staff's perceptions, emotional states, and social interactions to determine whether the given border technology will be adopted and accepted, and if so, how effectively. The toolkit will be able to support the prediction of technology acceptance for border control technologies from travelers' and border staff's perspectives.

Stages of the social sensing toolkit

It is divided into two stages: 1) agent-based modelling and simulation and 2) social sensing. Stage 1 is mostly related to creating synthetic data for the relevant data categories and manual rules, aiming to create the first set of simulations reflecting the travelers' as well as border staff's interaction and technology acceptance for border control technologies. Next, the synthetic data and manual rules will be updated with the data from the pilots to include real scenarios and actual technology acceptance rules. The data from pilots will be controlled data under certain conditions. This stage includes both synthetic and controlled data. Therefore, it will only serve as training for the agent-based simulation engine towards predicting the technology acceptance.

Stage 2 will use the data and rules information from other sources like online social networks, the web, expected data from BCPs to enhance further the learning/training of the agent-based simulation engine. As this stage has the real data, it will serve as a validation/testing part for the engine to assess its accuracy for predicting technology acceptance.

ABMS tool

For the Stage 1 activities, the ABMS tool needs to be chosen, with a set of needed requirements as follows:

- to allow the use of visual modelling languages, scripting, and extensibility
- to ease the development process
- to be open source
- to extend default models with Java
- to allow all types of simulations (Discrete/Continuous, Micro/Macro Level)
- to have a broad spectrum of capabilities – including multi-agent models
- to keep the model building process simple and clear

Based on these requirements, among a shortlist of possible tools, the final tool chosen was Anylogic. It is the only object-oriented M&S software that supports agent-based modelling techniques with prebuilt extendible and graphical libraries, as well as access to all Java API that enables for adding any specific functionality. Also, it is freely available at no cost, open-source and it is used easily compared to other agent-based simulation tools. Furthermore, AnyLogic is currently the most appropriate M&S tool for modelling in a modular, hierarchical, and incremental way, allowing systems to be represented to any level of detail.

Social sensing media source

For the social sensing part, a proper source is needed, able to support the identification of information patterns in the travelers' behavior to predict the level of acceptance of border control technologies. According to the functional requirements for the most appropriate social sensing media source, Twitter was selected in our case, due to the following reasons:

- In comparison to other social media platforms, the Twitter API is more open and accessible, making Twitter more appealing for creating tools to access data.
- Data from other social media platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn) are extremely difficult to obtain and are only available on an aggregate level for marketing purposes.
- When it comes to data collection, because Twitter has a strong hashtag culture, this makes it easier for gathering, sorting, and extending searches.
- Twitter creates an automatic database of information in real-time, which means that as it is archived, it will become a unique source of historical information.
- Twitter offers a search feature that allows users to look up tweets, and tweets also appear within Google search results; it is easier to find and follow conversations.

Datasets and data sources

As already mentioned, the main research goal is to assess users' acceptance of border control technologies as well as measure the efficiency of such technologies. Hence, there will be collected data concerning two different sets of "users": data related to travelers and those related to border control staff.

The toolkit will receive data originating from two categories of data sources:

- *Primary Data*: data that is collected directly from informed and consented "users" during the different activities. Such data originate from:
 - Questionnaires addressing specific questions about border crossing points, their control routines and technologies used.
 - Twitter: tweets (Twitter posts), while at the border control points, using a specific hashtag.
 - Mobile Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a mobile application.
 - Tablet Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a tablet application.
- *Secondary data*: data that is relevant to the research but has been collected in the past. Such data are already available to use in the context of the research project from existing sources. and originate from:
 - Statistical data originating from border crossing points' databases.
 - Twitter: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, perceptions and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.
 - Online reviews of BCPs on blogs/websites

Based on the design and the decisions made at this stage, we were able to continue with the work further and get some initial results, detailed in the next section.

4. Preliminary results

Some of the initial results are linked with the Anylogic tool used for the agent-based simulation phase. The tool was used to run demos based mostly on synthetic data, starting from basic information, such as age range, gender, country etc. Then, a given combination of such data could result in the user – traveler having different emotional states related to the given technology in use at the border control. Such combinations could result then in an initial set of rules, as expected for the Stage 1 of the social sensing toolkit.

Further on, the tool could benefit from the information extracted from the Twitter API. It would result in information related to user location, tweet time and possible hashtags included. The information retrieved could be useful when matched with current technologies being used or the overall acceptance level and other background information extracted from other sources.

There are more ongoing results, which are relevant to the research problem in questions, and thus be included in our future work on the same or similar direction.

5. Conclusions

The main purpose of this paper was to provide the basic grounds for the future stages of the innovative toolkit, designed to accommodate the objectives of our research, towards enabling better technologies for use by the border control authorities, when facing different profiles of travelers in and outside the EU area. On this purpose, the paper started with a review on the most relevant studies on the usage of different SBCTs, technology acceptance theories, ABMS approaches and social sensing methods across multiple domains. The main conclusions drawn from this process were related to an existing gap found in the study of user technology acceptance on SBCTs, followed by a gap in the study on the usage of ABMS or social sensing methods in the domain of SBCTs.

At this stage, the idea proposed was that of designing a social sensing toolkit, which would help support the main purpose of assessing travelers' and border control staff's perceptions, emotional states, and social

interactions to determine whether the given border technology will be adopted and accepted, and if so, how effectively. It is designed to cover 2 stages, as mentioned in the previous sections, while the next phases should be more focused on the specific modules expected, namely the Socio-cultural Framework, Automated Threshold Module and the Agent-based simulation tool.

Finally, the most important step is related to the transition between the existing synthetic data, created to help train the existing models, with the real-time data, expected to be collected at the border control points or from the authorities.

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